

Emergent ferromagnetism and interface exchange bias in self-assembled copper-fullerene hybrid nanostructures

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Abstract

Interface in the metal (Me)-C₆₀ multilayer (ML) appears to be a unique means of controlling local electronic and magnetic properties of hybrid materials. The remarkable ability of interface is discussed in [(2015) Nature 524:69], where a ferromagnetic (FM) state of the Cu-C₆₀ ML hybrid was found. In this work, we report the discovery of stable FM effects in the self-assembled (SA) Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid system possessing a large and controllable fraction of self-organized interface formed between single-crystal Cu nanoparticles and the C₆₀ medium. Using SQUID magnetometry, we were able to confidently establish the magnetization hysteresis loops, which reflect the FM state of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids even at room temperature. By applying the SA hybrid model, we performed the relevant normalizations of the magnetic curves, which allowed us to prove the decisive role of the interface Cu atoms in the FM magnetism of the SA hybrids. Field cooling (FC) of the SA sample to 2 K in the field of 1 T revealed a specific shift in the hysteresis loop, reflecting the exchange bias effect in the SA hybrid system. The anomalous increase in saturation magnetization in the SA hybrid after FC treatment indicates the magnetic effect of the C₆₀ monolayer pinned to the interfacial FM Cu layer by the exchange bias field. The obtained results designate the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids as multifunctional materials with tunable magnetism, promising for use in effective sensors and memory devices.

Keywords: Hybrid materials; Self-assembly; Interface; Magnetism; Exchange bias.

1 Introduction

In recent decades, considerable attention has been paid to the development and functionalization of various hybrid nanomaterials, which has revealed intriguing application potential of organic-inorganic hybrids (OIHs) [1-5]. Great hopes are placed primarily on magnetic OIHs, in which pronounced effects of magnetic field on the transport of spin-polarized electrons has been detected. Remarkable achievements in study of such effects have led to emergence of organic (molecular) spintronics as next-generation electronics, the principles of which are based on the exploitation of spin degrees of freedom through the design of appropriate OIH nanostructures [6-8]. The major events in the development of spintronic OIHs are certainly related to the successful fabrication of vertical organic spin valves consisting of an organic molecule (for instance, such as Alq₃ or C₆₀) layer (spacer) sandwiched between two ferromagnetic (FM) inorganic layers (electrodes), which demonstrated giant magnetoresistance even at room temperature [9-11]. These exciting results also revealed an important advantage of organic spacers in spintronics compared to inorganic ones due to their significantly longer spin relaxation time [7,12,13].

Recent trends in organic spintronics concerning the study of spin injection and spin polarization mechanisms demonstrate the crucial role of the metal-molecular interface in establishing the spin-related properties of OIH

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nanomaterials [14-17]. Accordingly, increased attention to the interaction between the electronic structure of the interface and spin polarization effects in magnetic OIH has led to the emergence of a new subfield of spintronics known as "spinterface" [18,19]. In the context of the present work, it is worth mentioning some relevant results devoted to the spinterface effects in OIHs built of C_{60} molecules, which indicate the enhanced potential of C_{60} in spintronics due to weak spin-orbit coupling and absence of hyperfine interaction in these monoatomic carbon molecules [10,13,20-23].

There are a number of published reports focusing on the correlations between the atomic structure and the electronic coupling effects at the interface of metal (Me)- C_{60} hybrid systems (usually fabricated as bilayers or multilayers, ML), which provide new insights into the interface-associated spin ordering affecting spin transport and magnetism in hybrid nanomaterials [24-35]. Most of these studies (experimental and theoretical) concern hybrid systems created from magnetic transition metals (FMs, such as Fe, Co, Ni) and fullerene due to the attractive features of FM- C_{60} coupling that affect the interfacial spin states. It was established that the adsorption of C_{60} molecules on the surface of 3d-metal leads to the molecule-metal chemical coupling, comprising the metal-to- C_{60} electron transfer and π (carbon)- d (metal) hybridization [24-29, 36]. Moreover, quantum mechanical simulations of the C_{60} -FM hybrid systems argue that such an interface coupling can cause reconstruction of the metal surface, which affects the electronic structure and magnetic properties of the materials at the interface [30-32,36,37]. It was reported that the interface coupling can induce magnetization of C_{60} molecules and suppress the magnetic moment of the FM metal leading to antiferromagnetic spin alignment at the interface [30-33]. Moreover, simulations of some FM- C_{60} systems revealed the formation of spin-split hybrid states at the C_{60} -FM interface, which induce symmetry-dependent spin polarization in the metal and fullerene near the interface [34].

An unusual magnetic hardening (known as "emergent magnetism") attributed to interface coupling has been discovered in the last decade during the study of the OIHs consisting of non-FM 3d-metal (such as Cu, Mn, Sc) and C_{60} layers [38,39]. Thus, when studying the magnetization of Cu- C_{60} multilayers produced by the conventional layer-by-layer vapor deposition, the authors of [38] identified hysteresis loops indicating the ferromagnetic behavior of the OIH. It was reported that the detected FM state of the hybrid material is localized in the near-interface Cu layer with a thickness less than 2 nm; at the larger distances from the interface, ferromagnetism is rapidly quenched [38,39]. The unusual ferromagnetism of the C_{60} -Cu OIH was understood as a crucial change in the quantum mechanical parameters of Cu d -electrons (such as the density of states and the exchange interaction integral) caused by the Cu- C_{60} interface electronic coupling [38,39].

It is worth noting that the electronic interaction at the interface, leading to the emergent magnetism in the Cu- C_{60} multilayer (ML) system [38,39], can be seriously affected by the interface structure disordering, the effect of which increases in the upper layers during the formation of the Cu- C_{60} MLs. Indeed, since the surface roughness of the Cu layer depends on the number of layers [38-40], the atomic structure of the interfaces created on different layers will not be identical that will seriously affect the electronic states providing the magnetic phenomenon.

In this work, we attempted to confirm the emerging magnetism and also to verify the role of the Cu- C_{60} interface in this magnetic effect applying the self-assembly phenomenon to create a specific Cu- C_{60} hybrid system.

To avoid the above-mentioned problem of ML hybrid systems, we studied the magnetism in the Cu-C₆₀ hybrids fabricated via the controlled self-assembly (SA). We applied an original experimental approach, exploiting physical vapor deposition and SA phenomenon [41-45] to fabricate well-reproducible Cu-C₆₀ hybrids with tunable nanostructures. The applied fabrication method yields the remarkable Cu-C₆₀ hybrid nanostructure as the uniform ensemble of small Cu nanoparticles (NPs) immersed in a C₆₀-based matrix. Unlike ML hybrids, such a specific nanostructure of the OIH formed through self-assembly includes a large (and controllable) fraction of the Cu-C₆₀ interface with identical atomic structure on any NP. The identity of the interfaces follows from the uniformity of the thermodynamic conditions in the depositing Cu and C₆₀ mixture and further self-assembly of Cu NPs in a C₆₀-based medium, stimulated by the Gibbs free energy gain [46]. Another important advantage of the created SA Cu-C₆₀ OIH nanostructure (as compared to the ML Cu-C₆₀ OIHs) is the ability to control the interface fraction and interparticle spacing. The above-mentioned advantages of self-assembled nanostructure prompted us to conduct a study of magnetic effects in SA Cu-C₆₀ hybrids with different nanostructure parameters, which allowed us to discuss the origin of the observed magnetization effects.

2 Experimental

Some details of the method for production of SA Me_xC₆₀ hybrid film are described elsewhere [41-43]. Here, thin Cu_xC₆₀ OIH films were fabricated by simultaneous deposition of pure Cu (99.99 mass. % Cu, Mateck) and pure C₆₀ (99.95 mass. % C₆₀, MER) on Si(100) substrates with a size of 5 mm × 10 mm at the substrate temperature of 100°C in high vacuum of 10⁻⁶ mbar. The deposition was performed from independent sources, namely from an electron gun (Cu deposition) and from an effusion cell (C₆₀ deposition), which proper operation controlled by digital controllers (FuG Elektronik) allowed us to adjust deposition rates to reach the required concentration of Cu, x , in the deposited Cu and C₆₀ mixture (x is a number of Cu atoms per one C₆₀ molecule). Control of quality of the depositing Cu_xC₆₀ films during deposition process was carried by quartz thickness monitor (deposition rate, r_d), effusion cell temperature (T_{ec}), electron beam current (I_{eg}), substrate temperature (T_s), and by vacuum control (P_v). The deposition parameters were kept constant during deposition process and were set as following: $I_{eg} = 16$ mA and 18 mA (for LC and HC, respectively); $T_s = 100^\circ\text{C}$; $P_v = 4 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar (working vacuum). Time of the deposition process was fixed as 600 s. Change of the depositing samples from LC to HC (as well as the parameter I_{eg}) was carried out in-situ without interruption of the deposition process (shutter was closed during the sample change). Between the experiments, the samples were kept in vacuum.

The value of x is verified by Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) analysis of the deposited Cu_xC₆₀ sample. In this study, we fabricated the Cu_xC₆₀ OIH samples with two Cu concentrations, namely $x=3.6$ (low Cu content, LC) and $x=8.5$ (high Cu content, HC). The RBS spectra were recorded using a 2 MeV He⁺-ion beam generated by a 6-MeV Tandemron accelerator in a vacuum of 10⁻⁷ mbar. The recorded RBS spectra were analyzed using SIMNRA computer code [47].

The nanostructure of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films was verified and studied by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a FEI Tecnai TF20 X-twin microscope operated at 200 kV. TEM images and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were recorded by means of a Gatan UltraScan CCD camera with a resolution of (2048 × 2048) pixels using a Digital Micrograph. The SAED patterns were evaluated using the Process-Diffraction software package [48]. Samples for TEM analysis were prepared by scratching the deposited Cu_xC₆₀ films on holey-carbon-coated Cu grids.

Raman spectra of the self-assembled Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films were recorded using the LabRAM HR Evaluation Raman spectrometer from HORIBA Scientific. The spectrometer is combined with confocal optical microscopy with a resolution of 1 μm. The excitation of the Raman spectra was carried out by SHG Nd:YAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm. The Raman spectra of the self-assembled hybrid films were recorded under ambient conditions at RT at a laser power density of 10 mW/cm².

Magnetic properties of the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} films were studied by a superconductive quantum interference device (SQUID) magnetometer (MPMS7 from Quantum Design) with a resolution of 10^{-8} emu and with highest magnetic field of 7 T. In the present experiments, the magnetic field, H , was applied with in-plane orientation relative to the Cu_xC_{60} sample. The magnetization curves $M(H)$ were measured with the cyclic variations of the magnetic field H with an amplitude of 0.2 T. The magnetization was studied at the different temperatures T in the interval from 100 K to 300 K and at 2 K.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Identification of the SA hybrid nanostructure

Before presenting the magnetometry results revealing the magnetic properties of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films, it is important to provide an understanding of the specific details of the nanostructure of the film formed by the self-assembly of the Cu_xC_{60} mixture. Valuable information was obtained using RBS and TEM methods, allowing the characterization of Cu_xC_{60} films.

Fig. 1 **a** RBS spectra of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films with $x=3.6$ (upper spectrum) and $x=8.5$ (lower spectrum). Experimental spectra are shown as black dots; simulated spectra are shown as red curves. **b** The depth profiles of the elements in SA Cu_xC_{60} films at $x=3.6$ (upper plot) and $x=8.5$ (lower plot), corresponding to the simulated RBS spectra shown in **a**.

Fig. 1 shows the results obtained by RBS. The RBS spectra shown in Fig. 1a allowed us to estimate the chemical composition and thickness of the films, which were preliminary estimated using a thickness monitor during the deposition process. As can be seen, the spectra clearly demonstrate the expected ion scattering effects from Cu (strong peak at 1530 keV) and from C_{60} (small peak at 490 keV), which are the main components of the hybrid films. The pronounced enhancement of the ion scattering yield observed at energies below 1090 keV is due to the Si substrate [41,42]. The mentioned features of the RBS spectra were reliably identified using SIMNRA modeling with an appropriate parameter setting [42,47]. The simulated RBS spectra are shown as red curves in Fig. 1a. The depth profiles of the sample models corresponding to the theoretical RBS spectra are shown in Fig. 1b. Only two elements (Cu and C) with the appropriate concentrations uniformly distributed throughout the sample depth were used in the models. Correctly performed adjustment of the Cu concentration, x , and the film thickness in the simulated Cu_xC_{60} films made it possible to obtain a fairly good match between the experimental RBS spectra and the simulated ones (see Fig. 1a). The present RBS analysis determines the Cu concentration in the LC and HC samples as $x=3.6$ and $x=8.5$, respectively. The film thickness is estimated to be 70 nm (for LC-sample) and 100 nm (for HC-sample) (see Fig. 1b).

Fig. 2 **a** TEM images of AS Cu_xC_{60} films with $x=3.6$ (top image) and $x=8.5$ (bottom image). **b** Plots of Cu NP size distribution obtained from analysis of the TEM images. Cu concentration, x , Cu NP mean size, d_c , and standard error, σ , are shown on the plot area. **c** Images of the SAED patterns recorded from the films with $x=3.6$ (upper pattern) and $x=8.5$ (lower pattern). **d** SAED pattern intensity plots obtained for the films with $x=3.6$ (upper plot) and $x=8.5$ (lower plot). Standard positions of diffraction peaks are indicated by vertical red dashed lines with arrows (for Cu) and by vertical dark-green dashed lines with diamonds (for C_{60}). **e** HRTEM images of AS films with $x=3.6$ (left image) and $x=8.5$ (right image). **g** HRTEM images of a single Cu NP, distinguishing the crystal lattice in the LC sample (left image) and in the HC sample (right image). The NPs are indicated by yellow circles.

The RBS analysis performed confirms the uniform distribution of Cu throughout the sample, indicating the successful deposition of the Cu_xC_{60} mixture films (x denotes the concentration of Cu in the mixture as a number of Cu atoms per C_{60} molecule [41-44]). The expected hybrid nanostructure is achieved by the self-assembly effects that transform the homogeneous Cu_xC_{60} mixture into a heterogeneous Cu_xC_{60} nanostructure as the uniform 3D-ensemble of small Cu NPs supported by the C_{60} -based matrix [41]. Direct information about the nanostructure of the fabricated self-assembled film was obtained by analysis of the deposited samples using transmission electron microscopy. The results of the TEM analysis are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2a shows the TEM images of the nanostructure of self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} mixture films obtained from the thinnest film fragments created by scratching. The images show numerous small black dots, evenly distributed in a whitish medium. Taking into account the chemical content of the films evaluated by RBS (see above) and using the concept of Z-contrast (the heavier the element the darker the contrast [49]), we should associate the observed black dots with Cu nanoparticles and the whitish medium with the C_{60} -based matrix. Detailed analysis of the NP sizes using ImageJ software (one hundred of NPs were analyzed) revealed the lognormal distributions of the NP sizes in the deposited samples, giving an average NP size of $d_c = 3.1$ nm (for the LC-sample, $x=3.6$) and $d_c = 4.2$ nm (for the HC-sample, $x=8.5$) with standard errors of $\sigma=0.025$ nm and $\sigma=0.032$ nm, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2b.

The chemical origin of the phases detected in the LC and HC samples by the TEM imaging (black dots and whitish medium) was proven using selected area electron diffraction (SAED), the diffraction patterns of which are presented in Fig. 2c (as the diffraction rings) and in Fig. 2d as graphs of the intensity of diffraction rings). The SAED pattern plots clearly identifies the existence of the fcc-C₆₀ phase revealing strong diffraction peaks from (022) and (224) planes (see the dark-green arrows and the vertical dashed lines, Fig. 2d) occurring in the low k range (here, k is the scattering vector). One can also see the remaining part of the strong reflection from the (111) plane of fcc-C₆₀ appearing very close to the central spot of the diffraction pattern. The intensity plot of the SAED pattern in the high k range (namely, $k > 25$ 1/nm) shows several peaks corresponding to pure Cu (the peaks are indicated by red arrows and by red dashed lines, Fig. 2d). It is obvious that the peaks found in the high k range of the pattern intensity plot denote the black dots in the TEM images as fcc-Cu NPs. The high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ film shown in Fig. 2e demonstrate the hybrid nature of the film nanostructure. Careful analysis of the HRTEM images confirms a single-crystalline origin of the Cu NPs, as evidenced by the uniform orientation of the crystal lattice planes throughout the nanoparticle. Fig. 2g shows the HRTEM images of selected Cu NPs in Cu_xC₆₀ samples with $x=3.6$ and $x=8.5$, in which the detected crystal lattice confirms the NP single-crystalline origin.

The conducted TEM analysis confirms the successful formation of the Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films, the nanostructure of which consists of C₆₀ molecules and fcc-Cu NPs. The surviving of C₆₀ molecules in the hybrid films was proven by Raman scattering experiments.

Fig. 3 **a** Raman spectra of SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films with $x=3.6$ (blue dots) and $x=8.5$ (green dots). For comparison, Raman spectrum of a pure C₆₀ film is also shown (red curve). The vertical red dashed lines indicate the standard positions of the main Raman modes of C₆₀, namely $H_g(7)$, $A_g(2)$ and $H_g(8)$. **b, c** Deconvolution of the Raman spectrum in the region of the pentagonal pinch mode (A_g2) obtained for the SA hybrid film with $x=3.6$ (**b**) and with $x=8.5$ (**c**). The numbers on the plot area indicate the position of the respective Lorentzian (in 1/cm) (see **b, c**).

It is well known [50] that Raman spectrum of C₆₀ in the range of the wavenumbers (ν) from 200 cm⁻¹ to 2000 cm⁻¹ ($\nu < 2000$ cm⁻¹) consists of ten Raman-active vibrational modes with A_g and H_g symmetry, some of which (namely, $A_g(2)$, $H_g(7)$ and $H_g(8)$ located at 1424 cm⁻¹, 1469 cm⁻¹ and 1573 cm⁻¹, respectively [50]) exhibit the highest intensity. Fig. 3a shows a comparison of the Raman spectra measured in the relevant ν range (including the most intense vibrational modes of C₆₀) from the LC and HC samples (upper green and blue dotted curves, respectively) with the spectrum of a C₆₀ film deposited on Si-substrate under similar experimental conditions (lower red curve). For easy comparison, the spectra are shifted along the vertical axis while maintaining the scaling of the intensity of the spectra of LC and HC samples. The intensity of the pure C₆₀ spectrum was reduced by a factor of 70 to keep the most

intense mode (i.e. $A_g(2)$) within the generated region of the graph. Comparison of the spectra in Fig. 3a shows that the most intense Raman modes of C_{60} , such as $A_g(2)$, $H_g(7)$ and $H_g(8)$ (the modes are indicated by vertical dashed lines) are detected in the Raman spectra of the SA Cu_xC_{60} samples, which proves the survival of C_{60} molecules in the hybrid samples during the self-assembly of the hybrid nanostructure.

At the same time, it can be seen that the vibrational modes associated with C_{60} in the Raman spectra of the hybrid films are changed seriously compared to the modes in the spectrum of the pure C_{60} film (see Fig. 3a). Even a cursory examination of the Raman spectra allows one to notice an increase in the width and a decrease in the intensity of vibrational modes associated with C_{60} in the spectra of the hybrid films, which is obviously due to the interaction of the molecule with the metal at the C_{60} – Cu NP interfaces [41,42,44]. The interaction can be quantitatively assessed by analyzing the broad peak observed around the position of the $A_g(2)$ mode in the spectra of the hybrid films (see Fig. 3a). The shape of this broad peak in the Raman spectra allows us to consider its complex structure (indeed, on the high-frequency shoulder of the broad peak, a sharp peak associated with pristine $A_g(2)$ is clearly observed, see Fig. 3a). Figures 3b and 3c show deconvolution of the Raman spectra of the Cu_xC_{60} film using a set of appropriate Lorentzians, which represent details of the broad peak, revealing three elementary peaks situated at 1469 cm^{-1} (filled with dark yellow), at 1459 cm^{-1} (filled with blue) and a small peak at 1464 cm^{-1} (filled with pink). Since the position of $A_g(2)$ is very sensitive to the charge state of C_{60} molecules [50], the detected Lorentzians indicate the formation of different C_{60} -based compounds in self-assembled hybrid films. The Lorentzian at 1469 cm^{-1} represents a pristine $A_g(2)$ mode indicating the existence of intact C_{60} molecules in the hybrid films. Obviously, such molecules are located in the hybrid film structure far from the metal-fullerene interface. The blue Lorentzian (at 1459 cm^{-1}) reflects the softening of the $A_g(2)$ mode due to the C_{60} charging through the transfer of electrons from the metal to the C_{60} molecule [50,51], which essentially occurs at the C_{60} -Cu interface during hybrid structure formation. A careful study of the correlation between the number of electrons transferred to one C_{60} molecule and the downshift of the $A_g(2)$ mode performed by several teams [50,52-54] revealed a nearly linear relationship, giving a coefficient of 6 cm^{-1} per electron. This relationship allows us to determine the interaction at the Cu- C_{60} interface in the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films by the value of the electron charge transferred from the Cu NP to the C_{60} molecule as $1.6e^-$, which correlates well with the results obtained from photoemission experiments with the C_{60} -Cu bilayers (estimated as $1.5 \pm 2 e^-$) [29,55]. The pink Lorentzian detected at 1464 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3 b,c) reflects another $A_g(2)$ mode downshifted by 5 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the compound with the C_{60} molecule charged by $0.8e^-$. Interestingly, the same charge transfer value was found in the simulation of the C_{60} -Cu bilayer using density functional theory (DFT) [26]. The detection of two downward-shifted Lorentzians can be explained by two preferred orientations of bound C_{60} molecules in respect to the Cu NP surface at the Cu- C_{60} interface (related, for instance, to molecule pentagon and hexagon) [24,38,56]. The analysis of the Raman spectra of the LC and HC samples shown in Fig. 3 is presented also in Supplementary.

The conducted analysis of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films proves the applicability of the hybrid nanostructure model developed in our recent works [41-45,57], which allows us to effectively discuss the structure-sensitive properties of the SA Me_xC_{60} hybrid films. In this model, the SA hybrid nanostructure is represented as the well-organized nanocomposite consisting of the ordered ensemble of metal NPs with the NP ordering in a simple cubic lattice (it is assumed that the spatial density of NPs in the modelled composite and in the real hybrid is the same) as

shown in Fig. 4. The smallest unit cell of such an ordered Me_xC_{60} hybrid nanostructure is a cube filled by one Me NP in the center and by a certain number of C_{60} molecules (determined by x [42-44]) in the remaining volume of the cube. The Me NP is approximated by a sphere with a size of $2R$ (R is the radius of the sphere). The size of the smallest unit cell is L . The shortest distance between the NPs is denoted as ΔL . All parameters of the SA Me_xC_{60} nanostructure ($2R$, L , and ΔL) depend on x [42-44]. The Me NP average size, $2R$, can be determined by TEM (see above). Determination of the unit cell parameters allows us to describe the nanostructure of the SA Me_xC_{60} hybrid and to facilitate understanding the origin of the material property.

Fig. 4 Model of the hybrid nanostructure formed through self-assembly of a Me_xC_{60} mixture. Metal NPs are shown as large red (solid and dashed) circles. Small circles filled by brown pattern correspond to C_{60} molecules. Cubes with NP in the center represent unit cells of the SA hybrid nanostructure. L is the size of the unit cell, which also corresponds to the distance between NPs (from center to center). ΔL is the shortest distance between NPs (from surface to surface). See text.

According to the model of the SA Me_xC_{60} hybrid film, the dependence of the unit cell size L and the interparticle distance ΔL on x can be described by the equations $L(x)=R(x)[(4\pi/3)(1+\beta/x)]^{1/3}$ and $\Delta L(x)=L(x)-2R(x)$, where $\beta=n_a/n_m$, n_a and n_m are the atomic density in fcc-Cu and the molecular density in fcc- C_{60} , respectively [43-45]. So, for the LC and HC samples we have $L_1=7.5 \text{ nm}$ and $L_2=6.8 \text{ nm}$. For ΔL , we can obtain the following $\Delta L_1=3.9 \text{ nm}$ and $\Delta L_2=2.6 \text{ nm}$. The average NP size for the samples is $2R_1=3.1 \text{ nm}$ (for LC sample) and $2R_2=4.2 \text{ nm}$ (for HC sample) as we obtained with TEM (see above). For the readers' convenience, the parameters of the SA sample hybrid nanostructures are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Parameters of hybrid nanostructure of the SA Cu_xC_{60} samples estimated with the RBS and TEM experiments using the original model (see Fig. 4 and Ref. [43-45]).

Sample name	x	$d_c=2R$ (nm)	L (nm)	ΔL (nm)
LC	3.6	3.1	7.5	3.9
HC	8.5	4.2	6.8	2.6

3.2 Magnetometry results: evidence of spontaneous magnetization

After identifying the nanostructure of the SA films, we can move to the magnetic effects detected in SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films using SQUID magnetometry.

Fig. 5 shows the cyclic magnetization curves, $M(H)$, obtained for the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films at different temperatures, namely 300 K (Fig. 5 a), 200 K (Fig. 5b) and 100 K (Fig. 5c). The magnetization curves were obtained for both samples, i.e., for the LC sample ($x=3.6$, blue curve) and for the HC sample ($x=8.5$, red curve). The scale on the vertical axis shows the absolute value of the total magnetic moment (M) of the samples. It can be seen

that the cyclic variation of H leads to the appearance of $M(H)$ hysteresis loops, confirming the ferromagnetic behavior of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids in the considered temperature range (from 100 K to 300 K), which is qualitatively consistent with the magnetization results obtained for the Cu-C_{60} ML samples, as reported by Ma'Mari et al [38]. Similar to the Cu-C_{60} ML samples, the $M(H)$ curves of the Cu_xC_{60} SA films show a saturation magnetization M , which is reached at the field H_s of about 1000 Oe (see Fig. 5 and Ref. [38]).

Fig. 5 $M(H)$ hysteresis loops obtained at the temperatures of 300 K (a), 200 K (b) and 100 K (c) for hybrid SA Cu_xC_{60} films with $x=3.6$ (blue curves) and $x=8.5$ (red curves). Diamagnetism of the Si substrate is subtracted.

The results of the magnetic experiment, presented in Fig. 5, allow us to compare the absolute values of the total magnetic moment of the SA Cu_xC_{60} samples at the saturation stage (i.e. non-normalized saturation magnetization, M_{0s}). It is evident that the M_{0s} value of the sample with higher Cu content ($x=8.5$) is significantly higher compared to the sample with $x=3.6$, even though the saturating field H_s is the same for both samples. This result alone indicates an important role of Cu in the observed ferromagnetism of the SA hybrid films confirming the idea of the emergent magnetism in Cu-C_{60} ML hybrids [38].

For a correct comparison of the magnetization curves obtained in this work for the SA Cu_xC_{60} films with those given in Ref. [38] for Cu-C_{60} ML hybrids, we normalized the total magnetic moment to the volume of the Cu NPs (V_{NP}) formed in the SA samples (in [38], the magnetic moment of the ML samples was normalized to the volume of the metal). We estimated the total volume of Cu NPs using our model of SA metal- C_{60} nanostructure (see text above and Ref. [41-45]), RBS results (estimation of film thickness and Cu concentration, x), and TEM results (estimation of Cu NP size). As a result, for the SA Cu_xC_{60} films with Cu concentrations $x=3.6$ and $x=8.5$, we find the amount of Cu NPs in the samples (N_{NP}) to be 8.13×10^{12} for the LC-sample and 15.58×10^{12} for the HC-sample, and the total volume of Cu (V_{NP}) to be $1.90 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^3$ and $6.05 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^3$, respectively (the total volume of Cu in the ML Cu-C_{60} samples in [38] is about 10^{-7} cm^3). The corresponding normalized $M(H)$ plots for the LC and HC samples (the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids) are shown in Fig. 6.

The normalization of the $M(H)$ hysteresis loops for the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films, obtained after measuring the cyclic magnetization curves at RT (see Fig. 6), yields two important outcomes. First, the performed $M(H)$ normalization using V_{NP} gives a good quantitative correlation between the magnetization curves measured for the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids (this work, see Fig. 6) and the curves obtained for Cu-C_{60} ML hybrids (see Fig. 1 in Ref. [38]). For example, the saturation magnetization, M_s , found for the Cu_xC_{60} LC and HC samples (at RT M_s is 56 emu/cm^3 and 50

emu/cm³, respectively, see Fig. 6) is in good agreement with that of the Cu-C₆₀ multilayer (52 emu/cm³, see Ref. [38,39]). A satisfactory correlation in the coercivity, H_c , was also established. In particular, H_c at RT for the HC sample is 61 Oe ($H_c \approx 72$ Oe for the Cu-C₆₀ ML hybrid [38]). These correlations also confirm the reliability of the model used to describe the nanostructure of the SA hybrid film. The correlations also suggest that the ferromagnetism of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids and the Cu-C₆₀ ML hybrids has the same origin, which can be explained by the order of magnetic moments of the Cu atoms near the interface, as reported in [38,39].

Fig. 6 $M(H)$ hysteresis loops normalized to the total volume of Cu NPs and obtained for SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids with $x=3.6$ (blue curve) and $x=8.5$ (red curve) at $T = 300$ K (RT).

The second important result concerns the significant reduction of the difference between the magnetization curves (hysteresis loops) of LC and HC samples after the applied normalization. A small difference is observed only at higher magnetic field (close to the saturation stage), where the magnetization of the LC sample is noticeably even higher than that of the HC sample, which has a higher Cu concentration.

The results obtained through normalization of the SA hybrid film magnetization are important for understanding the origin of the emergent ferromagnetism. If the electron spin states of Cu, which carry ferromagnetism in the hybrid films are the same in both (LC and HC) samples, then the applied normalization of the magnetization curves should lead to a complete coincidence of the hysteresis loops, regardless of the value x in the Cu_xC₆₀ films. However, some difference in the loops is observed at higher magnetic fields (in particular, at the saturation magnetizations, $M_s=50$ emu/cm³ and $M_s=56$ emu/cm³ for HC and LC samples, respectively), which might be associated, for example, with some differences in nanostructure of the LC and HC samples caused by the change in x [43,44].

The study of the magnetization of Cu-C₆₀ ML hybrid films by the authors of Ref. [38,39] and the similarity of their results with the results of the present work obtained for SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films allows us to associate the ferromagnetism detected in LC and the HC samples with the electronic coupling of Cu and C₆₀ at the interfaces. To test this assumption, we estimated the effective magnetic moment of the Cu atom for both samples (LC and HC), considering only the ordering of magnetic moments of Cu atoms at the interface. Using the SA hybrid nanostructure model, we can easily estimate the total number of Cu atoms on the NP surface (N_{sa}) as $N_{sa}=n_{sa}SN_{NP}$, where n_{as} is the

surface density of Cu (1.93×10^{15} at/cm²), S is the Cu NP surface area ($S=4\pi R^2$), and N_{NP} is the total number of Cu NPs in the sample. If the ferromagnetism is due only to Cu atoms located at the interface, then the magnetic moment of the surface Cu atom can be roughly estimated as $m_s(x)=M_s/N_{sa}$, where M_s is the saturation magnetization of the film. For magnetization at room temperature ($T=300$ K, see Fig. 5a), we obtain $m_s = 0.24 \mu_B$ (for the LC-sample) and $m_s=0.20 \mu_B$ (for HC-sample); here μ_B is the Bohr magneton. The quite satisfactory correlation between the results obtained for the LC and HC samples confirms the validity of our assumption, which also gives a reasonable value for the effective magnetic moment of the Cu atom at the interface in SA hybrids. The reduced m_s value in the HC sample (compared to the LC one) may be due to the negative influence of the Cu atoms in the NP bulk, which eliminates the ferromagnetism of the Cu atoms at the surface [38]. Indeed, the ratio (N_{sa}/N_{va}) of the number of Cu atoms on the NP surface, N_{sa} , to the number of Cu atoms in the NP volume, N_{va} , decreases with the x increasing from $x=3.6$ to $x=8.5$ (this ratio equals to 0.44 in LC versus 0.32 in HC). It is worth noting that the decrease in M_s in the HC sample compared to M_s in the LC sample, which arose after normalization, may have the same origin (see Fig. 6).

3.3 Magnetometry results: evidence of exchange bias magnetism

To examine the role of C_{60} molecules in the magnetism of Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films, we measured the magnetization of the SA hybrid sample at a low temperature (at $T=2$ K) after pre-cooling the sample from RT to the low T in a strong magnetic field of 1 T (or 10^4 Oe, a so-called field cooling experiment, FC). As noted in the Introduction, the electronic coupling between the C_{60} layer and the FM metal surface can lead to the appearance of a surface layer of the magnetic C_{60} molecules with an antiferromagnetic orientation of the magnetic moments of the molecules relative to the magnetic moments of the FM metal [30,33]. We expected that charge transfer and hybridization at the interface in the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids could also induce magnetism of C_{60} molecules, which could be recognized by the FC experiment.

Fig. 7 **a** Hysteresis loops $M(H)$ measured for a LC sample at $T=2$ K after cooling the sample in a field of $H=1$ T (FC loop, red curve). Normal $M(H)$ dependence of this sample measured at 300 K is shown for comparison (blue curve). **b** Enlarged central part of the hysteresis loops shown in **a**). The centers of normal and low- T FC loops are shown by black and red crosses, respectively. The shift of the FC loop center by -36 Oe relative to $H=0$ (center of normal loop) is shown by the horizontal black arrow. Vertical arrows show left and right coercivities, H_{c1} and H_{c2} . The dashed vertical line indicates the bias field, H_E . Diamagnetism of the Si substrate is subtracted.

Fig. 7a shows the FC magnetization curve, $M(H)$, measured for the LC sample ($x=3.6$) at $T=2\text{K}$ after cooling the sample from RT to 2K under the in-plane external field of 1 T (red curve). Similar to the results shown in Fig. 5, the FC $M(H)$ dependence measured at 2K (red curve) was obtained during cyclic variation of the magnetic field H (Fig. 7a). For comparison, this figure also shows the cyclic $M(H)$ dependence of this sample measured at RT (300 K) under normal conditions (blue curves).

As can be seen from Fig. 7a, the cyclic dependence of FC $M(H)$ at cryogenic temperature ($T = 2\text{K}$) also exhibits a hysteresis loop, the area of which is significantly larger compared to the $M(H)$ loop measured at RT (compare the red and blue loops in Fig. 7a). In particular, the coercive field and normalized saturation magnetization of the LC sample at 2 K are $H_c \approx 86$ Oe and $M_s \approx 83$ emu/cc, which are clearly larger than the respective values determined at RT (see above). The expansion of the FC magnetization loop measured at the low temperature can be understood using the spin wave (or magnon) model, which explains the effect of temperature on the spin order in ferromagnets [58]. Furthermore, the FC magnetization experiment yields a new attractive effect, revealing a -36 Oe shift of the low- T hysteresis loop along the H axis. This shift is clearly visible when comparing the FC $M(H)$ loops measured at 2K and the normal $M(H)$ loop measured at RT (see Fig. 7a). The magnified central part of the hysteresis loops is shown in Fig. 7b, where the shift of the FC-loop center is clearly demonstrated (the FC-loop center part shown by the vertical dashed line is shifted relative to $H=0$, which is the center of normal loop).

This shift of the FC $M(H)$ loop is a sign of the exchange bias effect, which usually occurs at the ferromagnet-antiferromagnet interface of inorganic hybrid materials [59,60]. Recently, the exchange bias has also been found in the layers of paramagnetic molecules deposited on the FM metal surface [61-63]. Thus, the detection of the exchange bias effect in the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid film allows us to conclude that there is a particular interaction between the FM Cu surface and the C_{60} molecules localized at the C_{60}/Cu interface. Considering the detected exchange bias effect, the C_{60} molecules and the FM Cu atoms can be antiferromagnetically coupled even under normal conditions (i.e., RT and no magnetic field). It is worth noting that the magnetic moment in the C_{60} molecule is associated with the extra electrons transferred from Cu to C_{60} due to the electronic coupling at the Cu- C_{60} interface (see Fig. 3 and Ref. [24]). A similar magnetic correlation, evaluated with DFT simulations and X-ray magnetic circular dichroism (XMCD) experiments was recently reported for the FM-metal-fullerene (namely, for the Fe- C_{60} and Co- C_{60}) layered hybrid systems [30,33].

The detected exchange bias in the AS Cu_xC_{60} hybrid can be interpreted as follows. Under the strong magnetic field ($\mu_0 H_{FC}=1$ T) applied to the hybrid film at RT, the magnetic moments of the FM Cu atoms on the NP surface and the magnetic moments of the interfacial C_{60} molecules are aligned unidirectionally along the applied H_{FC} field direction. After cooling the sample to the low temperature ($T=2$ K) in a strong field H_{FC} , subsequent measurement of the $M(H)$ curve yields a FC-influenced hysteresis loop, which occurs to be shifted along the field axis (see Fig. 7). This shift suggests the appearance of an additional field (exchange bias, H_E), which ensures FM alignment of the magnetic moments of C_{60} molecules and the FM Cu atoms at the C_{60}/Cu interface. Such an alignment of the Cu and C_{60} magnetic moments at the interface in the FC magnetization is manifested by the detection of the exchange bias field, H_E (here as $H_E=36$ Oe, see Fig. 7b), as well as by enlargement of the FC hysteresis loop area (see Fig. 7). The FM alignment of the C_{60} magnetic moment in the low- T FC magnetization experiment can be confirmed by the following discussion and arguments.

The magnetization curves of SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids, $M(H)$, measured at different temperatures (see Fig. 5), demonstrate a rather weak change in the saturation magnetization (M_s) with temperature, which argues a high value of the exchange integral J and, accordingly, a high Curie temperature T_c of ferromagnetic Cu. Using the experimental hysteresis loops shown in Fig. 5, we can plot the $M_s(T)$ dependence in the temperature range from 100 K to 300 K. In Fig. 8, such a $M_s(T)$ dependence is shown by dots (see the lower T part of the graph). Considering the condition of $T \ll T_c$ and the concept of magnon excitations as the main mechanism responsible for the temperature degradation of the FM spin order, we can apply the Bloch law in the form of $M_s = M_{s0} (1 - T/T_c)^{3/2}$ to describe the $M_s(T)$ dependence obtained for the HC sample shown by straight red line in Fig. 8a (here M_{s0} is the saturation magnetization at $T = 0$ K) [58,64]. The best fit between the dots by the red line in Fig. 8a is achieved by setting the Curie temperature to $T_c = 950$ K. Following the Weiss model of ferromagnetism (mean field model [58]), we can also use the widely accepted equation $M_s = M_{s0} C (T_c - T)^{1/2}$ to approximate the $M_s(T)$ dependence near T_c (here C is a constant). In Fig. 8a, the dotted line was obtained using this equation, assuming that the Curie temperature $T_c = 950$ K. As can be seen, the two approximations applied nicely correlate with the typical $M(T)$ dependence for a ferromagnet described by Brillouin function in the Weiss model [58].

Fig. 8 a, b Temperature dependences of saturation magnetization $M_s(T)$ (a) and magnetization $M(T)$ at $H = 200$ Oe (b), obtained for the HC sample using the experimental results (green dots, a, and thick green line, b) and the Bloch model equations (solid and dashed red lines, see text). **c** The $M_s(T)$ dependence obtained for a LC sample using a procedure similar to (a). The red point in (c), indicated by green arrow, corresponds to the M_s of the FC hysteresis loop measured at 2 K. T_c is a Curie temperature (see text).

We verified the evaluated Curie point (T_c) by measuring the FC $M(T)$ dependence while cooling the HC sample from 300 K to 100 K in a 200 Oe magnetic field. The obtained experimental dependence $M(T)$ is shown by the thick green line in Fig. 8b. Interestingly, despite the fact that the magnetization is far from saturation, the same approximated procedure gave a good match between the theoretical curve and the experimental dependence, if the Curie temperature is chosen as $T_c = 950$ K. Thus, assuming the Weiss model to describe the Cu ferromagnetism emerging at the interfaces in the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid, we obtain a fairly high value of the Curie temperature, $T_c = 950$ K (for example, for Fe $T_c = 1043$ K [58]). From this result, we can also estimate the strength of the emergent ferromagnetism, using mean field theory. In particular, the Weiss field B_W responsible for the spontaneous ordering of spins is defined as $B_W = \lambda M_s$, where the parameter λ (Weiss constant) can be calculated from the equation (1) [58]

$$\lambda = \frac{3k_B T_c}{N g^2 S(S+1) \mu_B^2} \quad (1)$$

Here, N is the atomic concentration, S is the spin number, g is the Landé factor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and μ_B is the Bohr magneton. Assuming for Cu, $N \approx 8.48 \times 10^{22}$ at/cm³ and $S = 1/2$, we have $\lambda \approx 1800$. Since, for saturation magnetization of Cu_xC₆₀ we obtained $M_s \approx 55$ Oe, strength of the mean field $B_W = 55 \times 1800 = 99\,000 \approx 10^5$ Oe (for Fe, $B_W \approx 10^7$ Oe [58]). The performed estimations yield the reliable value of the molecular field strength providing the FM Cu layer.

We can now return to the exchange bias to specify important details of the effect related to the magnetism of C₆₀ molecules. Fig. 8c shows the temperature dependence of the saturation magnetization, $M_s(T)$, obtained for the LC sample based on the study of magnetization curves measured at different temperatures (see Fig. 5). The experimental data points on the $M_s(T)$ plot were fitted to the corresponding equations using the same procedure we applied to the HC sample to estimate the Curie temperature, T_c (see Fig. 8a and corresponding text). In this case, the simulated curve perfectly matches the experimental points when we applied $T_c = 950$ K (see Fig. 8c). It turns out that the point corresponding to M_s at $T = 2$ K (determined in the FC magnetization experiment; red point in Fig. 8c) deviates significantly from the fitting curve, displaying a much larger M_s value (approximately, by factor 1.35) than the value suggested by the Bloch equation. Apparently, this anomalous increase in M_s is a consequence of the exchange bias, which can be understood as the effect of additional magnetic effect of the C₆₀ magnetic moments pinned by the exchange bias field on the interfacial Cu FM layer after all moments have been aligned unidirectionally by the strong magnetic field H_{FC} . Using the model of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ nanostructure (see above) and the magnetization results, we can estimate the effective magnetic moment of the C₆₀ molecule at the interface. Considering the size of Cu NP in the LC sample ($R = 1.55$ nm, estimated by TEM) and the number of Cu NPs (or number of unit cells) in the samples (8.13×10^{12}), estimated with the SA hybrid model, and also using the value of additional magnetization ΔM_e arising due to exchange bias (ΔM_e is about 0.4×10^{-5} emu, see Fig. 8c), and ascribing ΔM_e effect to two C₆₀ molecular layers at the interface, we can find the effective magnetic moment of the interfacial C₆₀ molecule as $m_{eff} = 0.25 \mu_B$. This value correlates well with the magnetic moment values of the C₆₀ molecule adsorbed on Fe (001), which were obtained using DFT simulations by the authors of the Ref. [31] ($m_s = -0.24 \mu_B$ in the case of unreconstructed Fe surface), as well as using DFT simulations and XMCD experiments presented in Ref. [30] ($m_s = -0.21 \mu_B$). The correlations between the simulated magnetic moment of C₆₀ in the FM-metal-C₆₀ ML hybrids and those obtained in this work for the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids prove reliability of the approaches used and the present results obtained. Furthermore, the estimation of the C₆₀ magnetic moments allows us to assume the existence of two C₆₀ magnetic monolayers at the interface with an antiferromagnetic (AF) mutual alignment, as it was established for the layers of MnPc molecules deposited on Co surface [61]. Just AF alignment of the interfacial C₆₀ monolayers leads to the cancelation of the C₆₀ magnetic effect on the normal magnetization of the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrids at elevated temperatures (100 K–300 K) revealing only the emergent Cu ferromagnetism via the obtained hysteresis loops.

So, the obtained results imply quite complex nanomagnetism in the SA Cu_xC₆₀ hybrid films induced by interface, detailed nature of which, however, could be untangled using different experimental approaches, such as study of the $M(H)$ and $M(T)$ dependences, field-cooling (FC) magnetization under various external fields. It is reasonable to expect that similar local magnetism in vicinity of interface can be generated in other SA Me_xC₆₀ hybrids (or even in ML Me_xC₆₀ hybrids) that can prompt the way to manipulate the local spin orders in such nanomaterials.

4 Conclusion

Self-assembled (SA) Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films with $x=3.6$ and $x=8.5$ were fabricated using physical vapor deposition to establish the unusual ferromagnetism (FM) generated by the Cu- C_{60} interface. Such a magnetism arising in non-magnetic 3d metal of the Cu- C_{60} multilayer (ML) hybrids was reported in Ref. [38]. In contrast to the ML systems, the SA hybrids consisting of very small Cu NPs and C_{60} supporting medium have a clear advantage in this case due to a well-controlled nanostructure, as well as a large fraction and uniformity of the interface, which is ensured by the phenomenon of self-assembly. Studying the magnetization of the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrids, we discovered the hysteresis loops indicating the presence of ferromagnetism in the hybrid films. Analysis of the $M(H)$ dependences using the SA hybrid nanostructure model shows an increase in the total magnetic moment with increasing x , i.e. with an increase in the interface fraction and Cu in the SA samples. By applying the appropriate normalization of the magnetic moment of the sample, we found a very good agreement between the hysteresis loops obtained from SA samples with different x , designating the interfacial Cu as the carrier of the emergent magnetism. Moreover, the good agreement between the normalized hysteresis loops and the $M(H)$ loop obtained in Ref. [38] for the ML hybrid confirms the same origin of magnetism in the SA and ML systems. Further normalization of the total magnetic moments of the SA samples at the saturation stage to the number of the surface Cu atoms made it possible to attribute the magnetism of the samples to the FM order of the magnetic moments of the interfacial Cu atoms and to estimate the magnetic moment of the atom as $m_a = 0.24 \mu_B$. The field cooling (FC) hysteresis loops measured at 2 K revealed the exchange bias-related shift and the unusual enlargement of the hysteresis loop, suggesting an additional magnetism of the C_{60} molecules at the SA hybrid interface that was induced by the exchange bias field. Using the saturation magnetization of the FC hysteresis loop, we estimated the effective magnetic moment of the C_{60} molecules as $m_{eff} = 0.25 \mu_B$, which correlates with the DFT simulation results of several groups. The obtained results designate the SA Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films as the multifunctional materials with tunable magnetism, promising advanced applications in spintronic devices, for instance in sensitive read heads and as the memory medium for high-dense information storage.

Supplementary Information

Authors' contribution Vasily Lavrentiev: conceptualization, methodology, samples fabrication, investigation, formal analysis, validation, writing the main manuscript. Alexandr Stupakov: investigation, formal analysis. Mariana Klementova: investigation, formal analysis. Karla Kuldova: investigation, formal analysis. Jiri Vacik: investigation, funding acquisition. Alexandr Dejnek: resources, methodology. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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Declarations

Competing interests. The authors declare no competing interests.

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